

Analysis of the structural composition of common aviation terms: a corpus-based study

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Abstract: This article aims to present the basic characteristics of the structural composition of 60 aviation terms which are often used by aviation professionals, and people interested in flying. We discuss the morphological composition of the terms, categorizing them into groups according to their specific features. Attention is paid to the essential role some of these terms have had in the expansion of the aviation terminological field.

Keywords: *aviation terminology, morphology, word formation, corpus linguistics*

1. Introduction

Technology and science have been developing rapidly during the 20th and 21st centuries, introducing new concepts and terms, thus enriching specialized languages. The aviation terminological field is not an exception. Man has always been enchanted by the idea of flying. That dream has led people to the development, and the invention of technologies used in their attempt to conquer the unknown. As a result, the aviation terminological field has been expanding. Nowadays, it comprises of terms that originate from Latin, Greek and Old French to terms which came into existence in the 20th century. There is no doubt that the field is still expanding since aviation language is developing, together with aviation itself.

The present research is based on a small corpus: 60 terms have been extracted from two chapters in the Pilot's Handbook of Aeronautical Knowledge, (Aircraft Construction and Aerodynamics of Flight), issued by the Federal Aviation Administration. Although these terms are randomly chosen, they all have something in common - they are often used among aviation professionals and we consider them to be among the key terms in the aviation terminological field. We are interested in finding out what the prevalent structural patterns among these terms are, analyzing the morphological processes such as affixation, compounding, and conversion. The topic of the word formation processes related to aviation English has been researched by Azis, Rosa, Kovtun and others.

2. Data and Methods

The terminology used in the two chapters is crucial for the understanding of the operation and performance of aircraft. The corpus consists of 60 essential aviation terms, and it is considered as preliminary data for future research work.

The methods used for the analysis are descriptive and quantitative. A descriptive method of research is used for the analysis of each term and categorizing it in terms of its morphological structure. The method is also utilized by the author to research the ability of some of the most used terms to participate in word formation processes in the aviation terminological field. Quantitative analysis is performed to show the most numerous types of nouns. Also, the software tool Sketch Engine is used for frequency counts and studying the modifiers and modified words.

3. Research

Terms can be examined from three perspectives: formal structure (pronunciation and morphology), semantic content (terms refer to objects in real world and the meanings they have is a set of descriptive features), and their functional point of view (grammatical category and distribution). The formal side of a terminological unit is called a designation or term. Terms are base-level phonological presentations which have a phonetic form. .. Morphologically, terms are structures of constituent morphemes which form the basis of meaning [1]. A term is a linguistic unit that can be analyzed into smaller, meaningful components, called morphemes. A morpheme is the smallest unit of language which has formal and semantic significance. Lexical units can be simple (they contain only one morpheme), or complex (they have more than one morpheme). The basic morphological structure of terms is the same with that of words. If the morpheme is simple, it coincides with the root. The term is called simple.

Morphology plays an important role in term formation. Various morphological processes can be applied to create a new term. We can talk about affixation, compounding, blending, conversion, and coinage.

4. Findings and Discussion

The terms used in the research have been analyzed to find which are the common morphological patterns presented in the corpus. Each term was categorized in terms of its characteristics. The following categories were formed:

- 1) Simple words.
- 2) Compound words.
- 3) Complex words and
- 4) Compound adjectives.

The result was quite interesting- most of the terms in the corpus are simple words (47%), followed by the compound and complex nouns (33% and 12% respectively). The lowest percentage of appearance in the corpus is 8%, that of the compound adjectives category. Figure 1 shows graphically the distribution of these classifications, used to describe the morphological structures in the corpus:

Fig. 1 Categories in the corpus

In our opinion, the highest percentage of simple words can be explained by the fact that the Pilot's Handbook of Aeronautical Knowledge is a book that provides the fundamental information that is essential for pilots.

4.1 Simple words

Some 86% of the simple terms in the corpus are nouns, while 14% are verbs. Some of the terms are used as both nouns and verbs. Only one term is used as a noun and an adjective. The following are given as examples:

- 'Climb'- as a noun 43 times, as a verb- 26 times.
- 'Bank' -as a noun 73 times, as a verb- 15 times.
- 'Dive'- as a noun 12 times as a verb- 4 times.
- 'Tail'- as a noun 42 times, as an adjective- 13 times.

These results confirm the well-known fact that nouns dominate in the field of aviation terminology.

According to the given data in Sketch Engine, 'yaw' is used only as a verb, and appears 41 times in the corpus. The particle that is once used with it, is 'around'. We compared the other two terms usually discussed with yaw- 'pitch' and 'roll' and the results were as follows:

- 'Pitch' is used 44 times as a noun and it is 4 times modified by 'geometric'. As a verb 'to pitch' can be seen 19 times, the particles 'down' and 'up' are used twice after it.
- 'Roll' is used as a noun 26 times and it also collocates with Dutch, thus creating the compound term 'Dutch roll' with the meaning of 'a combination of rolling and yawing oscillations that occurs when the dihedral effects of an aircraft are more powerful than the

directional stability'. As a verb 'to roll' is used only 7 times and the particle 'off' is used once after it.

Although the corpus is small- two chapters of a book and 60 aviation terms extracted from them, it is still surprising that 'pitch' and 'roll' are used as a noun and verb, but 'yaw' is met only as a verb. Due to the size of the corpus, a generalised conclusion cannot be reached, but it is worth researching how these three terms 'behave' in the terminological field.

As can be seen from the above results some of the simple words are more often used than the others. On analysing the occurrence of the terms in the corpus, it was found out that several terms are used more than 100 times whereas there are terms that can be seen only 5 times or less (*to taxi* (v) and *to land* (v) are used only once, *slat* (n) is mentioned in the corpus 5 times). Figure 2 shows the terms that are in the corpus more than 100 times.

Figure 2. The most frequently used terms in the corpus

The most frequently used term in the corpus is 'wing' (299 times), followed by 'flight' and 'lift' (249 and 237 times respectively), 'drag' appears 185 times, 'weight' 146 times, 'angle' 117 times and 'air' 111 times. Interestingly, three of the four forces that affect the aircraft while flying are included in the list. The fourth force 'thrust' is used 96 times. Overall, the results are not surprising since all these terms are considered to be key elements in the subjects of aircraft construction and aerodynamics. It is worth noting that these terms are often used in the formation of other aviation terms. Some will be discussed below.

'Wing' is the term that is mentioned most in the corpus. The fact that this term can be used in both aircraft construction and aerodynamics makes it really productive, for example, '*elliptical wing*', '*rectangular wing*', '*wing root*', '*wing planforms*'.

If we take the term 'flight', we can find a lot of examples of terms used in aviation theory, for example: '*flight path*', '*level flight*', '*straight-and-level flight*', '*transonic flight*', '*high-speed flight*', '*flight controls*', and so on.

'Drag' is another interesting example of compounding. It forms compound terms using specific modifiers to distinguish different types of drag: '*interference drag*', '*parasite drag*', '*friction drag*'.

'Angle' is really productive in the field of aerodynamics. We can talk about '*bank angle*', '*climb angle*', '*blade angle*', '*pitch angle*', and it is used with '-of' construction in '*angle of attack*' and '*angle of incidence*'.

'Air' is undisputedly one of the most commonly used with other words to form terms related to aviation: for example, '*aircraft*', '*airflow*', '*airborne*', '*airspeed*'.

4.2 Compound words

The second group that predominates in the corpus is that of the compound words. Compound words are two or more root morphemes combined to form a new word, which has a specific meaning. For example, the term 'wingtip' is a combination of 'wing '+'-tip'. Knowing the meaning of these two

words, the newly formed term is easily recognized, namely ‘the outer end of an airplane wing’. Most of the terms included in this category were introduced to aviation language at the beginning of the 20th century. Figure 3 shows how the patterns identified in this group are distributed in this category.

Figure 3. Patterns identified in the category ‘Compound words’

The patterns identified in this group are as follows:

- Noun + Noun- this pattern is 60% of all compound nouns in the group. Examples include:
 - ‘flight path’ (‘flight’+ ‘path’) with the meaning of ‘a line, course or track along which an aircraft flies’.
 - ‘airstream’ (‘air’+ ‘stream’) with the meaning of ‘the flow of air caused by the movement of the aircraft through the air’.
 - ‘airflow’ (‘air’+ ‘flow’) with the meanings of ‘1.) The movement of air over the aircraft as it travels through the atmosphere. 2.) A current of air flowing through or past an object or body’.
 - ‘boundary layer’ (‘boundary’ + ‘layer’) with the meaning of ‘the layer of fluid next to the surface over which it is flowing and, because of friction, travelling more slowly than layers further from the surface’.
 - Verb+ particle- this pattern is 15 % of all compound nouns.
 - ‘touchdown’ (‘touch’ + ‘down’) meaning ‘the moment, after a flight, when the aircraft makes control contact with the landing surface’.
 - ‘takeoff’ (‘take’+ ‘off’) with the meaning ‘the procedure when an aircraft leaves the ground’.
 - Verb+ -ing+ Noun– this pattern makes up 10% of all compound nouns.
 - In the structure Verb + -ing, an adjective is formed which modifies the noun that follows it.
 - ‘leading edge’ (‘lead’ + -ing + ‘edge’) meaning ‘the front part of the wing which meets the oncoming air first’.
 - ‘trailing edge’ (‘trail’ + -ing + ‘edge’) meaning ‘aft part of an aerofoil.’
 - Two terms are formed by the combining form ‘alti-:’ altitude’ and ‘altimeter’. The prefix ‘alti-’ is a word-forming element meaning ‘high’ from Latin ‘altus’, literally ‘grown tall’.
 - ‘altitude’ means ‘the vertical distance between the aircraft, or a point or a level, and mean sea-level’.
 - ‘altimeter’ means ‘a radio instrument for measuring vertical distance or altitude’.
- Another interesting example of combining form is *gyro-* in ‘gyroscope’. This word-forming element is of Greek origin with ‘gyros’, meaning ‘a ring, circle’. The meaning of ‘gyroscope’ is ‘a device consisting of a spinning wheel, mounted on a base so that its axis can turn freely in one or more directions and thereby maintain its own direction even when the base is moved’.

When a close look is taken at the compound terms used in the corpus and their definitions, one would find that the combinations of the terms describe the new terms, and the new meaning is a result of this description. For example, 'touchdown' – the verb 'touch' shows that the aircraft touches something which is revealed by 'down' – something which is down i.e. the land. Leading edge- 'leading' is formed by the verb 'to lead' (to be in front) and -ing, 'edge' is the outer part of something.

4.3 Complex words

The third representative group in the corpus is that of complex terms. Complex term means a word that consists of a root (base form) and one or more affixes.

The terms used in the corpus have the structure root+ suffix. The suffix is used to change the part of the speech or the meaning of the term. Some interesting examples can be found.

→ '*winglet*' consists of 'wing' + '-let': -let is a diminutive noun-forming element, that originates from Old French ('-elet'). The meaning it conveys is 'small one'. It changes the definition of 'wing' from 'the main horizontal aerofoil or mainplane' to 'an upturned wing tip or small additional vertical aerofoil on a wing tip'.

→ '*spoiler*' is formed by the verb 'to spoil' and the suffix '-er'. This suffix is an English agent noun ending, corresponding to Latin '-or'. It provides the following meanings: 1.) person occupationally connected with 2.) person or thing belonging to or associated with 3.) one that does or performs (a specified action). The meaning of 'spoiler' in aviation is 'a hinged surface on the upper wing which, when opened, decreases lift and increases drag'.

→ '*Elevator*' is formed by the verb 'to elevate' and the suffix '-or'. The suffix '-or' is of Latin origin and it is added to verbs to form nouns. It indicates the person or thing that performs the action. 'Elevator' has the following meaning: 'a movable control surface, usually attached to the horizontal stabilizer of an aircraft, used to produce the nose up/down motion of an aircraft in level flight known as pitch'.

It can be concluded that the used suffixes have changed the terms' grammatical categories and modified their meanings.

4.4 Compound Adjectives

The compound adjectives category is the smallest group in the corpus. A compound adjective comprises two or more words which modify the noun. Two of the compound adjectives 'nose-up' and 'nose-down' can be found in the corpus used as nouns, but we have decided to include them in this category because of the highest number of occurrences of these terms as adjectives. Examples include:

→ '*... this nose-down attitude*'; '*... overcome the nose-down pitching tendency*';

→ '*a nose-up moment is produced*'.

The adjective that is most often used in the corpus is 'supersonic' which appears 10 times. For example:

→ '*supersonic flow, supersonic airstream*'.

Researchers have already demonstrated that nouns, verbs, and prepositions predominate in aviation texts. The percentage of adjectives is low, which is also confirmed by this study.

5. Conclusion

This corpus-based research revealed various structural pattern characteristics for texts related to aviation. It also provided some insights into how aviation terms are constructed: there were examples of compounding, conversion, and derivational affixes. It was found out that most of the terms included in the corpus are simple terms and some of them take part in word formation processes in the terminological field.

Understanding the morphological structures of aviation terms enhances professionals' skills to comprehend aviation terminology better and grasp term meanings more easily which leads to more effective communication and reduce ambiguity.

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